
Application of Jute Knitted Fabric for Desert Cooler

S. K. Soni, Shruti Donge, Samiksha Rokade & Shilpa Patil

Department of Textile Engineering, Jawaharlal Darda Institute Engineering and Technology, Yavatmal, Maharashtra, India 445001

Corresponding Author - S. K. Soni

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Abstract:

This study focuses on replacing wooden wool used in desert cooler side panel by the Jute yarn knitted structure. Jute is the most affordable and available nature bast fiber, composed of cellulose and lignin material. Water pads of desert cooler which are generally made up of wooden wool can be replaced by the Jute knitted fabric base water pads which are made by hand knitting. All the drawbacks and problems of wooden wool pads are eliminated by the jute knitted fabric. Due to which it increases the cooling efficiency of the desert cooler. It also provides acoustic insulation which reduces some amount of noise coming through the cooler. Jute knitted fabric base water pads will develop a new area for the knitting industries. Knitted fabric of 800GSM is manufactured and some of the properties like-Thickness, GSM, water permeability, air permeability, porosity, water absorbency, etc. for 800, 1000 and 1200 GSM of pads were tested and discussed. Which can affect the cooling efficiency of jute nonwoven pads.

Keywords: *Desert cooler, Wooden wool, Jute knitted fabric.*

Introduction:

Cooling devices are one of the most important devices for the people tropical countries like India during summer season. Desert cooler is effective and efficient when the dry bulb temperature is high and the relative humidity is low, restricting its use to dry climates. The temperature rises up to 45°C to 47°C and at some places like Delhi and Chandrapur the temperature goes up to 49°C. [1] Therefore, it is necessary to cool down the temperature at home, office, industry or any other working places. For lowering down the temperature, cooling devices like desert cooler and air-conditioners are used, where desert cooler is a cheaper option as compared to air-conditioners. They cost about 80-85% less as

compared to air conditioners, thus making them very cheap to install. For a 200 sq. feet room, a right sized desert cooler would cost about Rs 6000-8000 whereas an air-conditioner would cost about Rs35000-40000. Even if we compared electricity consumption, air coolers consume 80-90% less electricity as compared to air conditioners. The organized desert air cooler industry is estimated to be approximated Rs2600 crore in terms of value and it was estimated to have sold 3 million units in FY2019-20 in India.[2]

The normal size cooler (4x3) required 1Kg of wooden wool for making of cooler water pads for single unit then it requires 30 lakh Kg of wooden wool for manufacturing of 3 million units of desert cooler which is a huge

quantity. The wooden wools are extracted by cutting trees. Therefore, it is not environmentally friendly to cut huge number of trees for fulfilling the requirement of wooden wool. Also, the life of wooden wool is hardly 1-2 seasons.

To save the environment and stop the deforestation, in the study Jute yarn knitted structure is used and replaced wooden wool. Jute is one of the most important natural fibers after cotton in terms of cultivation and usage. It is most affordable and readily available fiber. The moisture regain of jute is high (13.75%). All the drawbacks and problems of wooden wool panels can be eliminated by the jute knitted fabric.

Material and Method:

For present study, crossed stockinette knitted structure is prepared by hand-knitting. This structure gives sufficient openings as well as bulk which helps in better cooling efficiency of the desert cooler. Knitted fabric of 800 GSM is manufactured using 82 jute count yarn. (82 pounds per 14000 yd.) In the commercial cooler, wooden wool is kept in between two metallic mesh which has problem of corrosion. To overcome this problem, synthetic mesh and nylon filaments are used outside and inside respectively to hold knitted structure.

Crossed stockinette knitted structure produced by hand knitting for 3 panels of size 4 × 3 feet and attached to the cooler and calculated its cooling efficiency in a room of 200 square feet.

Fig No. 1: Stockinette Knit Structure

Result and Discussion:

The cooling efficiency of cooler will conclude the overall results. The dry bulb temperature and wet bulb temperature (Indoor and outdoor) readings are obtained to calculate cooling efficiency. These two parameters will help to calculate the cooling efficiency of cooler.

1. Instrument used to measure the temperature:

A whirling hygrometer is used to evaluate the amount of water vapor in the air. It consists of two glass thermometers containing a liquid, usually mercury. One thermometer measures ambient air temperature (atmospheric temperature) while the other one measures the wet-bulb temperature (saturation temperature).

Fig No.2 Whirling Hygrometer

Two Whirling Hygrometers one each for outdoor and indoor are used. Outdoor and

indoor temperatures are recorded in the interval of 15 min, for 3 hours. Cooling

efficiency is calculated using following formula.

$$\text{Cooling Efficiency \%} = \frac{\text{DBT Outdoor} - \text{DBT Indoor}}{\text{DBT Outdoor} - \text{WBT Indoor}}$$

Where: DBT Atmosphere = Ambient air temperature (atmospheric temperature).

WBT = Wet bulb temperature (saturation temperature).

Table 1: Wood Wool Cooling Efficiency Test

Time	Indoor		Outdoor	Cooling Efficiency
	Dry	Wet	Dry	
2pm	32	24	40	50
2:15pm	29	23	41	70
2:30pm	28.6	30	42	81
2:45pm	28	22	42.4	74
3:00pm	27.5	22.5	41	72
3:15pm	27.5	21	41.5	68
3:30pm	27.5	21	42	69
3:45pm	27.5	21	43	70
4:00pm	27	20.5	40	66
4:15pm	27.5	21	38.5	59
4:30pm	27	20	38	61
4:45pm	27	20.5	37.5	61
5:00pm	27	20	37	58

Table 2: Jute Knitted Fabric Pad Cooling Efficiency Test

Time	Indoor		Outdoor	Cooling Efficiency
	Dry	Wet	Dry	
2pm	33	23	41	44
2:15pm	28	23	41	72
2:30pm	27	22	40	72
2:45pm	27.6	22	40	68
3:00pm	27.2	22.4	41	74
3:15pm	27	21	40	68
3:30pm	27	21	40.2	68
3:45pm	27	20	40	65
4:00pm	26	20	39	64
4:15pm	26.8	19	39	61
4:30pm	26	19	37	61
4:45pm	27	19.5	36	54
5:00pm	22.6	19	36	78

Conclusion:

We can reduce environmental pollution, support farmers and local artisans, and promote traditional crafts, which can also improve the cooling efficiency of desert cooler. Thus, desert coolers which are manufactured using knitted fabric instead of wooden wool are eco-friendly, long lasting, and give better cooling efficiency as compared to existing wooden wool-based coolers. It will be environmentally friendly and also it will increase the demand for the textile industry. This will lead towards increase in the growth of textile sector.

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